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Psychological And Social Correlates Of Job Satisfaction Among Caregivers In Early Orphanage Homes In Ikwerre Local Government Area Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated psychological and social correlates of job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study adopted the correlational research design. The study was guided by three research questions and three corresponding null hypotheses. The population of the study comprised 803 caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. A sample size of 267 caregivers was drawn through the simple random sampling technique. A self-designed questionnaire titled "Psychological and social correlates of job satisfaction questionnaire (PSCJQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated through face and content validities by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test reliability method and the reliability co-efficient of 0.76 was obtained. Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) statistics was used to answer the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study revealed that motivation and social support were positively significantly related to job satisfaction among caregivers in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. It was recommended among others that the government should improve the working conditions of caregivers in early orphanage homes for improved job satisfaction.

Keywords: Psychological, Social, Job Satisfaction, Caregivers

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is a critical aspect of organizational psychology, serving as a cornerstone for understanding employee motivation, employee engagement and overall well-being in the workplace. Essentially, job satisfaction is an individual's subjective evaluation of his or her work experience, encompassing feelings of contentment, fulfillment and happiness derived from his or her job roles and work environment (Baxi & Atre, 2024). Understanding the nuances of job satisfaction is paramount, as it not only influences individual attitudes and behaviours, but also has profound implications for organizational success and performance outcomes.

The relevance of job satisfaction cannot be overstated as it is intricately linked to several critical organizational outcomes. Research has consistently demonstrated a strong association between job satisfaction and employee retention, productivity and job performance (Baxi & Atre, 2024). Satisfied employees are seen to exhibit higher levels of commitment, engagement and discretionary effort, which,

in turn contribute to enhanced organizational effectiveness and competitive advantage. Exploring the dimensions of job satisfaction reveals its multidimensional nature, encompassing various facets that shape individual's overall satisfaction with their work. Key dimensions include intrinsic factors such as the nature of the work itself, autonomy and opportunities for skill development and growth. Extrinsic factors including compensation, job design, leadership and management, also significantly influence job satisfaction.

Hernity (2024) defined job satisfaction as a measure of an employee's contentedness with their job, the feeling of enjoyment or fulfillment that person derives from their job. It is measured in behavioural, cognitive and affective components. High job satisfaction in the workplace is beneficial for both the employee and the employer. Job satisfaction explains how much an employee is self-motivated, content and satisfied with his or her job

Maxwell (2016) defined job satisfaction as the employees overall feelings about their jobs. It is the state of well-being and happiness of a worker concerning performance in the workspace and its environment. Job satisfaction happens when employees feel like they have a stable job, room to grow in their career and a good mix between work and personal life. Employee job satisfaction is essential for organizations. Employee satisfaction can stimulate positive energy, creativity and increased motivation to succeed.

Meier and Specter (2015) posited that job satisfaction is a person's overall evaluation of his or her job as favourable or unfavourable. It reflects an attitude towards one's job and hence includes affect, cognitions and behavioural tendencies. Job satisfaction is a widely studied and central variable in many theories about organizational phenomena, and it is related to many factors that are important for human resource management such as performance, counter productive work behavior, turnover, and employee health.

Job satisfaction is assumed to be an antecedent of several organization relevant outcomes, some of which concern employee productivity and others that concern employee health and well-being. In the productivity side, job satisfaction has been linked to job performance, organizational citizenship behavior (behaviours beyond required job tasks that help the organization), counter productive work behavior (behavior that harm organizations) and withdrawal including absence and turnover (Specter, 1997).

The job satisfaction of caregivers in early orphanage homes is affected by certain psychological and social variables. Motivation is a psychological variable that affects the job satisfaction of caregivers in early orphanage homes. Motivation is primarily concerned with the individual's desires and how they can be fulfilled in the work situation. Amah (2016) defined motivation as the psychological forces within a person that energize, direct and sustain that person's effort towards goal attainment. Motivation determines the possible voluntary behavior an individual could engage in among different alternatives. It also determines the intensity an individual will be willing to put in to achieve a particular goal. Motivation explains why people behave the way they do in organizations (Amah, 2016).

Motivation is very important because highly motivated caregivers can produce twice as much as what poorly motivated caregivers will produce. With adequate ability and a good understanding of the job, well motivated caregivers tend to be satisfied in their job and highly productive. John (2020) investigated the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction of primary school teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. The result of the study revealed that motivation was positively significantly related to job satisfaction of primary school teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. Similarly, Nwiyi et al., (2012) carried out a study on the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in pre-school centres in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Occupational stress is also psychological variable that affects the job satisfaction of caregivers. The issue of occupational stress among caregivers in early orphanage homes has been a major concern among educational stakeholders. This is because in early orphanage homes, stakeholders have expressed concern on the issue of occupational stress which has seriously affected the job satisfaction of caregivers. Smith and Baurke (2020) viewed occupational stress as a subjective negative reaction to aspect of the job that threatens a worker's self-esteem or well-being. Occupational stress or workplace stress is the change in one's physical or mental state in which response to workplace poses an appraised challenge or threat to

that employee (Bright, 2015). Occupational stress results when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources or competencies of the worker. Echebe (2014) posited that occupational stress affects adversely job satisfaction of employees or workers in an organization. Amadi (2021) investigated the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Abia State. The result of the study revealed that occupational stress was negatively significantly related to job satisfaction of public senior secondary school teachers in Abia State.

Social support is a social variable that affects job satisfaction of caregivers. Social support refers to social and psychological support that an individual receives or perceives from his or her environment (Mash, 2016). He identified two major aspects of social support: received social support and perceived social support. The received social support refers to the degree to which a person has received support from his or her environment; the perceived social support refers to the perception and availability of this support. Social support has proven to be a very important factor in the organizational field. It has been not only related to positive individual outcomes such as positive affect (Mash, 2016), but also to a buffer against stress. Social support aids caregivers to cope with problems, improving positive psychological and behavioural responses. Moreover, recent research has shown that social support programmes in the workplace are related to employees' job satisfaction (Jacobs, 2022), Gift (2021) investigated the relationship between social support and job satisfaction among primary school teachers' in Rivers State. The result of the study showed that social support was positively significantly related to job satisfaction among primary school teachers in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Current institutions of learning are concerned with promoting job satisfaction among their employees. Job satisfaction is the extent to which individuals like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs. It results from individuals' perception and analysis of their job, influenced by their own distinctive desires, values and expectations they think are vital to them. The interest in job satisfaction stems from its major impact on employees' outcome, long-term work success and it is direct link to an employee's happiness. Being satisfied with work is one important indicator of wellness of employees in an organization.

However, caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State may not be satisfied in their jobs owing to poor motivation, high level of occupational stress and lack of social support from the environment. When caregivers are not effectively and efficiently motivated, they may not be well-satisfied in their jobs. Also, when caregivers experience role conflict, work overload and poor work conditions they may not be well-satisfied in their jobs. It is against this background the researcher investigated psychological and social correlates of job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of the study was to investigate psychological and social correlates of job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. In specific terms, the objectives of the study were:

1. To determine the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. To determine the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. To examine the relationship between social support and job satisfaction among in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were stated to guide the study

1. What is the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State?

3. What is the relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were stated to guide the study

1. There is no significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Theoretical Position

This research work was based on the job characteristics model. The job characteristics model explains that job satisfaction occurs when the work environment encourages intrinsically motivating characteristics. Five key job characteristics: skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback influence three psychological states: meaningfulness of work, responsibility of outcomes and knowledge of results.

Subsequently, the three psychosocial states then lead to clear number of potential outcomes, including job satisfaction. Therefore from an organization's point of view, it is thought that by improving the five core job dimensions, this null subsequently lead to a better work environment and increased job satisfaction.

METHODS

The correlational research design was adopted for this study. This design sought to determine the relationship between psychological and social correlates and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of 803 caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. A sample size of 267 caregivers in early orphanage homes was drawn from the population using the simple random sampling technique. Data were generated using a self-structured instrument with a modified four-point Likert scale. Face and content validities were used in this study. Professionals in measurement and evaluation and content specialists vetted the questionnaire items and considered them fit for the study. The reliability of the measuring instrument was determined using test re-test reliability method and the reliability co- efficient of 0.76 was obtained. Data used for this study were collected from the administered self-structured questionnaire. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics was used to answer the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Data presented in the study were based on the results of research questions answered and the tested hypotheses

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 1: Relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in Early Orphanage Homes

Variables	N	Σx	Σy	Σx^2	Σy^2	Σxy	r	Df	Calt-value	Critt-value	Rmk
Motivation	267	2200	335	97190	23445	67610	0.74	388	12.80	1.96	Not Sig
Job satisfaction											

Data in Table 1 revealed that obtained or calculated t-value was 12.80 while the critical t-value was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and at degree of freedom of 380. Since the obtained or calculated t-value (12.80) was greater than the critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance and at a degree of freedom of 388, the null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. On the other hand, as the motivation of caregivers increases, there is also a corresponding increase of their job satisfaction.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwrre Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State

Table 2: Relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes

Variables	N	Σx	Σy	Σx^2	Σy^2	Σxy	R	Df	Calt-value	Critt-value	Rmk
Occupational stress	267	944	949	60942	61605	60310	-0.30	388	-1.481	1.96	Not Sig
Job satisfaction											

Data in table 2 revealed that the obtained or calculated t-value was -1.48 while the critical t-value was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and at degree of freedom of 388. Since the obtained or calculated t-value (-1.48) was lesser than the critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance and at a degree of freedom of 3889, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state was accepted. This revealed that the alternate hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State. On the other hand, as occupational stress of caregivers increases, there is also a corresponding decrease of their job satisfaction.

Research Question Three: *What is the relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State?*

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state.

Variables	N	Σx	Σy	Σx^2	Σy^2	Σxy	r	Df	Calt-value	Critt-value	Rmk
Occupationa stress	267	2460	325	62463	21610	67624	0.76	388	14.81	1.96	Not Sig
Job satisfaction											

Data I table 3 revealed that the obtained or calculated t-value was 14.81 while the critical t-value was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and at degree of freedom of 388. Since the obtained or calculated t-value (14.8) was greater than critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance and at a degree of freedom of 388, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Obio/Akpor local government of Rivers state was rejected. This revealed that the alternate hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Obio/Akpor local government area of Rivers state. On the other hand, as the social support of caregivers increases, there is also s corresponding increase of their job satisfaction

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the results presented in the study, it was revealed that there was a high positive correlation between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of rivers state. The implication of the foregoing is that effective motivation significantly influenced job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state. The result of this study is in agreement with that of John (2020) and Nwiyi et al., (2021) who in their separate studies found that motivation was positively significantly related to job satisfaction.

From the result presented in the study, it was also revealed that there was a low negative relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state. The implication of the foregoing is that social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state. The result of this study is in agreement with the study of Amadi (2021) that occupational stress had low negative relationship with job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Abia State.

From the result presented in the study, it was also revealed that there was a high positive relationship between social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state. The implication of the foregoing is that social support influenced job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers state. The result of this study is in agreement with the study of Gift (2021) who found out that social support was positively significantly related to job satisfaction among primary school teachers in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions are drawn that there is a high positive relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State, there is a low negative relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State and there is a high positive relationship between g social support and job satisfaction among caregivers in early orphanage homes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the result of the findings:

1. The government should improve the working conditions of caregivers in early orphanage homes so as to motivate them for improved job satisfaction.
2. Caregivers in early orphanage homes should seek counseling to deal with occupational stress, through the application of inoculative and therapeutic stress management techniques.
3. Social support should be provided by parents, the government and well meaning individuals to boost the morale of caregivers for improved job satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- Amadi, V. (2021). Occupational stress and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Abia State. *Abia State Journal of Counselling*, 2(1), 38-41.
- Amah, E. (2016). *Human resource management*. Amethyst & colleagues Publishers.
- Baxi, B. & Atre, D. (2024). Job satisfaction, understanding the meaning, importance and dimensions. *Journal of management and Entrepreneurship Research*, 18(2), 34-40.
- Bright, M. N. (2025). *Fundamentals of human resources management*. Digital Press.
- Echebe, T. (2014). *Psychology of stress management*. Seaside Publishers.
- Gift, M.T. (2021) Social support and job satisfaction among primary school teachers in Rivers State. *Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 4(2), 10-18.
- Mash, O. (2016). *Introduction to industrial psychology*. New Heights Publishers.
- Maxwell, T. (2016) *fundamentals of organizational behaviour*. Pearls Publishers.
- Smith, O. & Bourke, T. (2020). *Introduction to stress management*. Pearls Publishers.
- Meier, L.L & Spector, P.E. (2015). Job satisfaction: A theoretical analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 6(2) 11-21
- Spectur, P.E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes and consequences*. Sage Publishers.
- Nwiyi, S., Daniel, A. & Amadi, S. O. (2021). Motivation and job satisfaction among caregivers in pre-school centres in Port Harcourt metropolis. *Journal of primary Education Studies*, 10(2), 40-51.